

Long-term data for Europe

EURHISFIRM

D8.1: Questionnaires and questions for semi-structured interviews
(Report)

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Background

The first objective of WP8 is to develop and run a large-scale survey, via an online questionnaire, in order to ascertain the preferences of potential users and key stakeholders for the design of data and services that EURHISFIRM RI should provide. In designing the survey, we have presented it at two EURHISFIRM consortium meetings and taken on board the views of the members of other work packages and the steering committee.

Survey design

We have designed a survey that will enable us to capture the following information:

1. The institution and position of the individual filling out the survey. This will help us see differences (if any) between the preferences of stakeholders. The preferences of academics may differ from those of policymakers and investment institutions.
2. The next part of the survey aims to capture the periods and geographies of most interest to stakeholders. This will allow the overall project team to think about the weight to put on different geographies and epochs. In this section and in each of the following sections, we ask participants to choose whether each option is 'Not Useful', 'Quite Useful' or 'Very Useful'. We also ask participants to rank their top two preferences. This will allow us to discern which data is most valuable, especially if most or all categories are ranked as 'Very Useful', while also enabling participants to fill in the survey quickly.
3. We then want to ascertain the data types and asset classes that would be of greatest interest to users. In particular, we want to know how useful access to accounting data, governance data, equity and bond data and macroeconomic data, would be.
4. We then want to discover exactly what type of corporate and financial data would prove most useful within each of these categories. In particular, what specific accounting variables will be of most use to end-users. We survey participants around the obvious data (i.e., total assets, profits, revenues, and debt), but also give them opportunity to suggest other data that they might find useful. We then ask questions on what specific equity and bond market variables would be of most interest. With the increased interest in corporate governance, we also ask about the usefulness of governance data such as board size. Finally, we ask questions to discover any specific macroeconomic variables end-users would like to access through the platform.
5. The next step of the survey covers how end-users will interface with the EURHISFIRM database. The first step will be to ascertain the databases the end user currently uses and their experience of using those databases in terms of ease of use, data availability, bulk downloads and value for money. We will also want to ascertain what they find most time-consuming when using existing databases. The second step aims to discover how useful it would be if the EURHISFIRM database was integrated with various software packages typically used in the analysis of corporate and financial data: Excel, Stata, R, SPSS, and Python. The third step will be to ascertain how important

it is for the end-user to have access to the original image, highlighted outliers, summary statistics, and graphed individual series, in order to assess the accuracy of data. The participant will also have the opportunity to add any further suggestions they may have.

The survey can be found at <http://www.eurhisfirmsurvey.eu/>. The survey takes about 10 minutes maximum to complete.

Next steps

Having just recruited a postdoctoral research fellow, we will be in a position to begin conducting the survey the coming weeks.

The survey recipients will be those identified in the network inventory exercise from Deliverable 2.3 (Inventory of European and national distribution networks).

